

European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative

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L4 SST analyses

CMEMS product ID: SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024

Issue: 2.3

Contributors: Simon Good

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CHANGE RECORD

Issue	Date	§	Description of Change	Author	Validated By
1.0	January 2017	All	Creation of the document	Simon Good	
1.1	March 2017		Responses to review; addition of logos and licensing information.	Simon Good	
2.0	12 April 2019	All	Update ESA SST CCI analyses to version CDR2.0	Simon Good	
2.1	10 September 2019		Added C3S ICDR2.0	Simon Good	Mercator Ocean
2.2	10 September 2020		Extension to 2019 and upstream data change	Simon Good	Bruno Buongiorno Nardelli
2.3	15 January 2021	II	Temporal extensions	Simon Good	Bruno Buongiorno Nardelli

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I EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

I.1 Products covered by this document

SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024: European Space Agency (ESA) Sea Surface Temperature (SST) Climate Change Initiative (CCI) and Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) analyses – global analyses of the sea surface temperature at 20 cm, representing approximately the daily average. The product is described fully in [RD.1] and [RD.2].

I.2 Summary of the results

The quality of the product will be described in detail in [RD.3] and is also presented in [RD.4]. In summary, robust statistics of differences between the analyses and reference datasets are used to assess both the sea surface temperatures and their uncertainties.

Summary statistics show that the median difference between the analyses and drifting buoy reference data ranged from -0.05 to -0.02 K, depending on the period and reference data subset that was used. Robust standard deviation ranged from 0.24 to 0.30 K.

Uncertainty estimates were validated by comparing the spread of the differences between the analysis data and the reference data to the spread expected from the combination of the uncertainty in the reference data and the analysis uncertainties. This was done for different levels of analysis uncertainty in order to check whether the uncertainties were well represented across the range of possible values. In general the analysis uncertainties were found to be well represented but with some underestimation of low uncertainties in the earlier part of the data record and some overestimation of high uncertainties.

I.3 Estimated Accuracy Numbers

Please see the ESA SST CCI validation results [RD.3] and the C3S Product Assessment Report [RD.4] for full information on the accuracy of the products.

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II PRODUCTION SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Production centre name

Met Office (as part of the ESA SST CCI project)

Description

The ESA SST CCI and C3S reprocessed analysis product is a satellite SST analysis created using the OSTIA (Operational SST and Sea Ice Analysis) system from re-processed (A)ATSR, SLSTR and AVHRR data as part of the ESA SST CCI and C3S projects. It can be accessed through CMEMS in addition to the dissemination methods provided by the originators. Its key features include its stability and its independence from in situ data for the recent period.

The product is available from 1st September 1981 to 3-4 months behind real time on a global regular grid at 0.05° resolution. This reprocessed analysis product provides an estimate of the SST at 20 cm. The inputs to the system are SSTs at 10:30 am and pm local time which means that the analyses roughly correspond to the daily average SST.

This product is distinct from the near real time and reprocessed SST analyses produced as part of CMEMS, which provide estimates of the foundation SST and uses more input data sources to provide the best analysis globally on any single day.

Additional information on the product is contained in [RD.1]. A full user guide is provided in [RD.2].

Please note that the products are made available under a Creative Commons Attribution license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Please cite [RD.1] and the dataset DOI if using the data. See the product user manual and http://licences.ceda.ac.uk/image/data_access_condition/esacci_sst_terms_and_conditions.pdf for full details.

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III VALIDATION FRAMEWORK

The data were comprehensively assessed as part of the ESA SST CCI and C3S projects. A full report of the ESA SST CCI work will be available in [RD.3]. Results presented here are summary statistics.

Products were evaluated against independent and pseudo-independent SSTs (i.e. including data used in algorithm development work) from drifting buoys, tropical moored buoys, Argo and ship-borne radiometers.

Note that assessments reported here are made using robust statistics comparing the data to the reference observations i.e. the median and robust standard deviation are used instead of mean and standard deviation. The robust measures are used because they are not as affected by the presence of outliers as the alternatives.

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IV SYSTEM'S NOTICEABLE EVENTS, OUTAGES OR CHANGES

Date	Change/Event description	System version	other
July 2019	Update to ESA SST CCI version CDR2.0.	CDR2.0	
December 2019	Add C3S ICDR2.0	ICDR2.0	
December 2020	Add 2019 data. Analyses for 2019 are based on data from the AVHRR sensor on MetOp-A and SLSTR on Sentinel 3A and 3B (for comparison, 2018 was based on AVHRRs on NOAA-19 and MetOp-A and SLSTR on Sentinel 3A).	ICDR2.0	

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V QUALITY CHANGES SINCE PREVIOUS VERSION

CDR2.0: Data covers 09/1981 to 12/2016

ICDR2.0: Data covers 01/2017 onwards

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VI REFERENCES

Ref.	Document Name	Document Reference	Issue	Date
[RD.1]	Merchant, C.J., Embury, O., Bulgin, C.E. et al. Satellite-based time-series of sea-surface temperature since 1981 for climate applications. <i>Sci Data</i> 6 , 223 (2019) doi:10.1038/s41597-019-0236-x			2019
[RD.2]	ESA SST CCI Product User Guide (http://www.esa-sst-cci.org/PUG/pdf/SST_CCI-PUG-UKMO-201_Issue_2-signed.pdf)	SST_CCI-PUG-UKMO-201	2	2019
[RD.3]	G. Corlett et al. 2020, Validation of independent satellite-based time-series of sea-surface temperature since 1981 for climate applications using SIRDS, in prep.			2020
[RD.4]	C3S Product Assessment Report (http://datastore.copernicus-climate.eu/documents/satellite-sea-surface-temperature/v2.0/D2.SST.2-v2.1_PQAR_of_v2SST_products_v3.1_APPROVED_Ver1.pdf)	D2.SST.1-v2.1_PQAR_of_v2SST_products_v3.1	3.1	2019